

Synthesis of Some New Sulphonamide Derivatives as Antibacterial Agents

SURENDRA BAHADUR*, NEERU SRIVASTAVA and MUKTA SAXENA

Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow, Lucknow-226 007

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A series of 2-phenyl-3-(4-N-substituted sulphonamido)phenyl-6,8-substituted-4(3H)-quinazolinones has been synthesised by the condensation of 2-phenylbenzoxazinones and sulphonamides in pyridine. The compounds have been screened for their antibacterial activity.

SULPHONAMIDES are drugs of proven therapeutic importance and are used against a wide spectrum of bacterial ailments¹⁻⁴. Schiff bases derived from sulphonamides are reported to be bacteriostatic^{5,6}. Since quinazolinone derivatives too are associated with antibacterial activity, it was considered of interest to incorporate the sulphonamido moiety in the quinazolinone nucleus to study if such a compound could be antibacterial.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary and are not corrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 137G spectrophotometer ($\nu_{\max}$ cm^{-1}) in KBr pellets and nmr spectrum in CDCl_3 on Varian A-90D instrument using TMS as internal standard (chemical shift τ , ppm). The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc.

2-Phenyl-6,8-substituted benzoxazinones (I) were synthesised by reported method⁷. Different sulphonamides were obtained from commercial sulpha drugs as described below. The compounds were synthesised by the following scheme.

Extraction of sulpha drugs :

Sulpha drugs, sulphadiazine and sulphapyridine were extracted by method (A) and sulphaguanidine by method (B).

(A) 0.5 g of the drug was powdered and triturated with two successive quantities of 5 ml chloroform. The residue was triturated with 10 ml dil. ammonia solution for 5 min and 10 ml water was added. The filtrate was then warmed to expel most of the ammonia. On cooling and acidification with acetic acid it yielded a solid which was dried at 100°.

(B) 0.5 g of sulphaguanidine was powdered and triturated with two successive quantities of 5 ml chloroform. The chloroform was rejected and the residue was further triturated with 10 ml dil. HCl, 5 ml water was added and filtered. The filtrate, after addition of a solution of ammonium acetate (3.0 g) in water (30.0 ml) was allowed to stand in a cool place for 30 min, when a solid separated out which was washed with water and dried at 105°.

2-Phenyl-3-(4-N-substituted sulphonamido)phenyl-6,8-substituted-4(3H)-quinazolinones (II) :

In a typical reaction, a mixture of 2-phenylbenzoxazin 4-one (2.23 g; 0.01 mole) and sulphanilamide (1.52 g; 0.01 mole) was refluxed in pyridine (15 ml) for 6-8 hr. A syrupy mass obtained on distilling off the excess of pyridine which was poured into crushed ice containing 5 ml conc. HCl. The separated solid was filtered, washed with cold water and recrystallised from acetone.

Fifteen compounds thus synthesised are listed in Table 1.

Bioassay :

Antibacterial activity : All the synthesised compounds and the parent drugs were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. typhi*, *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus*⁸.

Incorporation of quinazolinone nucleus in sulphonamides enhances their activity against *S. typhi* (vide entries 9 and 15). None of the sulphonamides

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA AND ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF 2-PHENYL-3-(4-N-SUBSTITUTED SULPHONAMIDO)-PHENYL-6,8-SUBSTITUTED-4(3H)-QUINAZOLINONES (II)

Sl. No.	R'	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Yield %	Antibacterial activity†		
					<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
R=R'=H							
1.	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂ S	157	61	—	—	12.0
2.	2-pyrimidino	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₇ O ₂ S*	227	65.0	—	—	8.0
3.	4,6-dimethyl-2-pyrimidino	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₂ S	180	63	—	6.0	6.0
4.	guanidino	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₂ S	225	65	—	—	6.0
5.	2-pyridino	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S	200	64.8	—	8.0	12.0
R=Br, R'=H							
6.	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₂ Br	214	62	8.0	10.0	10.0
7.	2-pyrimidino	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₇ O ₂ SBr*	235	69	8.0	—	—
8.	4,6-dimethyl-2-pyrimidino	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₅ O ₂ SBr	217	68	—	10.0	6.0
9.	guanidino	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₂ SBr	205	64	12.0	12.0	10.0
10.	2-pyridino	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ SBr	226	71	—	—	12.0
R=R'=Br							
11.	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₂ SBr ₂	174	62	—	10.0	10.0
12.	2-pyrimidino	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ N ₇ O ₂ SBr ₂	205	65	8.0	6.0	8.0
13.	4,6-dimethyl-2-pyrimidino	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₂ SBr ₂	186	67	—	—	6.0
14.	guanidino	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂ SBr ₂	225	64	—	—	12.0
15.	2-pyridino	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ SBr ₂	140	61	11.0	13.0	12.0
	Sulphadiazine				—	—	8.0
	Sulphadiazine				—	—	6.0
	Sulphaguanidine				—	—	12.0
	Sulphapyridine				—	—	—

† Zone of inhibition in mm.

All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

 * IR (cm⁻¹): 2. 1660 (-N-C=O quinazolonyl), 1580 (C=N), 1320 and 1160 (-SO₂NH-); 7. 1660 (-N-C=O quinazolonyl), 1580 (C=N), 1330 and 1160 (-SO₂NH-). NMR (τ): 2. 2.1-3.5 (multiplet, Ar-H), 0.5 (-SO₂NH-).

inhibit *B. subtilis* while compounds 6, 8, 9, 11 and 15 are specifically active against this organism. *S. aureus* is inhibited by all the synthesised compounds except compound no. 7 and the activity of sulphonamides against *S. aureus* is either retained or enhanced by the incorporation of quinazolinone nucleus except compound no. 6. As far as the substitution of bromine at positions 6 or 8 of quinazolinone is concerned no definite conclusion can be drawn.

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